

Role of inertia in short range depinning

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Abstract

The depinning transition occurs if an elastic interface is driven over a disordered pinning potential. A pinned–moving phase transition happens at a critical force via large reorganizations called avalanches. What happens to this transition in the presence of inertia is debated. We argue that, also with inertia, avalanches are power law distributed at a critical force that is very close to the minimum of the non-monotonic flow curve. At higher forces, avalanche nucleate an instability if their extent is larger than a critical length whose scaling we predict.

1 Introduction

The physical properties of a material are often controlled by the interfaces embedded in it. This is the case for dislocations in crystalline materials [1–3], crack fronts in fracture [4], frictional interfaces [5], or domain walls in magnets [6]. If the dynamics is dissipative (e.g. sliding charge density waves [7], vortex lattices in superconductors [8] and domain walls in ferromagnets [9]) many of these interfaces display a universal phenomenology. In the absence of temperature, the interface is pinned by impurities, but undergoes a *depinning transition* [10–12] at the critical force (or stress, or magnetic field), and moves via large reorganizations called avalanches. At higher forces, the interface moves at a finite rate.

In other systems (e.g. the frictional interface [13, 14], crack fronts in brittle materials [15], motion of contact lines of droplets on dirty or rough solid surfaces [16], and wetting of a rough surface [17]), the dynamics are not dissipative and inertial effects can be important. The difference between the overdamped and inertial dynamics is well understood by considering the local pinning potential landscape. Ref. [18] formulates this as follows: During elastic loading, the interface climbs up energy barriers, but then abruptly slides downhill once the barrier is overcome. For overdamped systems, this descent suffices to dissipate the energy stored during loading, while at lower damping the inertia may carry the system over several successive barriers leading to force (or stress) overshoots and oscillations. Such oscillations emit acoustic waves, which are, indeed, abundantly observed for example when a frictional interface slips (e.g. in earthquakes).

The consequences of inertia on the depinning transition have been debated. It is accepted that the flow curve (force f vs velocity v) becomes non-

monotonic [18–20] with a minimum at $f = f_{\min}$, as sketched in Fig. 1a. The subject of debate is if hysteresis is observed [19, 21, 22] and how this relates to avalanche-like events [22–24].

Figure 1. [Sketch] (a) With inertia, the flow curve (force f vs velocity v) is non-monotonic, with a minimum at $f = f_{\min}$. (b) A finite hysteresis is predicted in the thermodynamic limit, such that a system driven quasistatically through a weak spring displays stick-slip. Thereby, power law distributed avalanches protect the interface from building up a load $f > f_c$ where it is unstable. After the instability, the interface unloads to $f = f_{\min}$ while slipping (see corresponding cycle in panel a with the same colour coding).

A finite hysteresis corresponds to “stick-slip” under quasistatic loading, as sketched in Fig. 1b, whereby the interface is driven using a weak spring whose position \bar{u} is fixed. In the stick-slip cycle, the interface starts and stops moving at a different force. Schwarz and Fisher [22] argued that the interface is unstable at the force that it starts moving, such that the failure of a single microscopic region can run away and cause a macroscopic event, reminiscent of a first-order phase transition. Instead, the same authors later argued [25] that the nucleation of an instability occurs through an avalanche-like event of finite extent, reminiscent of a second-order phase transition. Furthermore, their numerics [25] indicated that hysteresis would vanish in very large samples. Conflictingly, Maimon and Schwarz

[26] again observe a finite hysteresis despite also suggesting that the phase transition is second order.

Supporting the possibility of a second-order transition, broadly distributed avalanches are observed also with inertia. It has been observed that the avalanche size distribution follows a power law $P(S) \sim S^{-\tau}$. Earthquakes are a commonplace example where such a distribution and acoustic waves are observed together [27]. Notable observations are that for an amorphous solid, the exponent τ is markedly increased by inertia compared to overdamped dynamics [23, 24]. Moreover, for a sand pile model with inertia, it was observed that abnormal large events become the dominant mechanism of relaxation if the system size is increased [28]; reinforcing a link between avalanches and the nucleation of an instability as suggested by Ref. [25].

Concrete ideas about the stability of a perturbation come from continuum theories based on velocity-weakening friction models. In particular, the non-monotonic flow curve, as in Fig. 1a, has been observed in rock sliding experiments [29], and was captured by rate-and-state models of the frictional interface [5, 30–33]. The stability of such a model can be studied by perturbing a stable solution with a moving region of extent ℓ (known as a “slip pulse”). It was found that an instability¹ can occur at a force $f_c > f_{\min}$ [35, 40] if the extent of the perturbation $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-1}$ [35]. The interface then moves and finally stops at f_{\min} . This supports a finite hysteresis but not clarify its amplitude as the microscopic origin of the perturbation is not considered.

We propose that, in the presence of disorder, avalanches constitute these perturbations. We already argued this in the presence of disorder, long-range elasticity, and bulk inertia [41, 42]; we confirm our picture here for an elastic interface with short-range elasticity and inertia. In particular, for quasistatic loading using a weak spring, we find criticality at f_c , such that the avalanche size, extent, . . . , are distributed according to power laws. Furthermore, we find that an avalanche is unstable if its extent $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$. In an infinitely large system, the interface is thus protected from building up a load $f > f_c$. If an instability occurs, the system advances by a large reorganization, and unloads to f_{\min} (the minimum of the flow curve), resulting in the stick-slip cycle in Fig. 1. Thereby, we numerically find that $f_c \approx f_{\min}$ in very large systems (see also [35, 40, 42]). Crucially, the disorder is responsible for a distribution of barriers f_c resulting in a self-affine roughness of the interface,

¹Once the instability is triggered, a ballistic fracture-like instability propagates [34–39].

which can be related to criticality to the non-trivial exponent ν .

In a finite system, the stick-slip amplitude is increased due to armouring by inertia [41, 43]. In particular, we find that if the interface stops after a system spanning event, there are very few regions with a small activation energy in the forward direction. Consequently, the number of avalanche is reduced, such that the interface can build up a load $f_s > f_c$, Figs. 2a and 2b. The scarcity of avalanches thereby masks the criticality of the interface, as a bimodal event size distribution is observed instead, see Fig. 2c, indeed argued to be the distribution of earthquakes on a single fault [44]. To study the properties of avalanches in an infinite system, we trigger avalanches at different forces f as study their statistics. At f_c their properties are scale free, while at $f > f_c$ avalanches transition to system spanning events if their extent $\ell > \ell_c$, see Fig. 2d. We predict and test $f_s - f_c$ as a function of the system size and the exponents τ, ν , and that of the distribution of activation barriers.

Figure 2. [Sketch] (a–b) In a finite system with disorder, avalanches occur at any force $f \geq f_{\min}$. They nucleate slip once their extent $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$, typically at $f = f_s$. (c) The corresponding distribution of event sizes, $P(S)$, during a quasistatic cycle is bimodal, see panel c, with avalanches up to a scale $S_{\max}(f_s)$, and system spanning events at a much bigger scale. (d) To study the properties of avalanches in an infinite system, and to quantify ℓ_c , we trigger avalanches at different forces f . The distribution of their linear extent ℓ is scale free at f_c while at $f > f_c$ avalanches transition to system spanning events if $\ell > \ell_c$ (system spanning events are excluded from the shown distributions).

2 Model

Dynamics. We consider a model with N particles numbered $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Each particle follows Newton dynamics, whereby we use a mass $m = 1$ that is uniform. The degree of freedom is the posi-

tion u_i such that its dynamics is:

$$m\ddot{u}_i = \underbrace{-\partial_u U_i}_{1)\equiv f_i^p} + \underbrace{\Delta u_i}_{2)\equiv f_i^n} + \underbrace{k_f(\bar{u} - u_i)}_{3)\equiv f_i^f} - \underbrace{\eta\dot{u}_i}_{4)\equiv f_i^d}. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\dot{u}_i \equiv \partial_t u_i$ is the particle's velocity and $\ddot{u}_i \equiv \partial_t^2 u_i$ is the particle's acceleration. The restoring force on a particle i is composed of the following terms. 1) Each particle is driven through a potential energy landscape U_i that is piecewise linear elastic with uniform elastic constant $\mu = 1$ and random local barriers, see below. 2) Neighbouring particles interact elastically such that schematically $f_i^n = \Delta u_i$, the Laplacian of u . We use the fourth order expansion due to [45, 46] such that in $d = 1$ dimensions, $f_i^n = k_2[u_{i-1} - 2u_i + u_{i+1}] + k_4[(u_{i+1} - u_i)^3 + (u_i - u_{i-1})^3]$ with $k_2 = k_4 = 1$ (see Appendix A for a derivation). Moreover, we assume periodic boundary conditions² such that $u_0 = u_N$. Note that we express length in units of the discretization, such that the system's extent $L = N$. We consider $d = 1$ span a large range of system sizes. 3) We drive by connecting each particle with a weak spring of stiffness k_f to a “driving frame” whose position \bar{u} is prescribed, see below. 4) Finally, we add a small damping term with uniform viscosity η to each particle. Underdamped dynamics correspond to $\eta^2 < 4\mu m$. We use $\eta = 0.1$. We study this model numerically by integrating Eq. (1) using the velocity Verlet algorithm, which uses a discrete time step $\Delta t = 0.05$ ³. See Fig. 3 for a schematic of the model for $N = 5$ particles.

Disorder. For each particle, the potential energy landscape U_i is a sequence of parabolic wells with uniform curvature $\mu = 1$ and random widths (that are quenched). The elastic force $f_i^p = \mu(u_i - u_i^{\min})$, with u_i^{\min} the position of the local minimum $u_i^{\min} = (u_i^s + u_i^{s+1})/2$ with $u_i^s = \sum_{y=1}^s u_i^y$ the position of the edge of the well that the particle is currently in. The width of the well, $u_i^{s+1} - u_i^s$, is drawn randomly from a Weibull distribution with shape parameter $k = 2$ ⁴. A crucial quantity is the force needed to fail locally in the forward direction, $x_i \equiv \mu(u_i^{s+1} - u_i)$.

Quasistatic loading. Quasistatic loading corresponds to driving the frame \bar{u} at a zero rate $\partial_t \bar{u} = 0$. In practice, we increase \bar{u} by a small amount and

² $u_{N+i} = u_i$ for any i .

³Such that $\Delta t \ll \omega^{-1}$, with $\omega^2 = \mu/m - (\eta/(2m))^2 \approx 1$.

⁴The cumulative distribution of the widths w is $\Phi(w) = 1 - \exp(-(w/w_0)^k)$ with $k = 2$ and $w_0 = 2$. A small offset of 10^{-5} is added such that $w > 0$ (i.e. $\Phi(w \leq 0) = 0$). Note that the average width is $\langle w \rangle \approx 2$, such that the typical yield force is approximately 1 (as we use stiffness $\mu = 1$). Finally, the sequence of wells for each particle i is offset by a random number, such that the local minima around $u_i = 0$ are not correlated.

Figure 3. Schematic of the model with equation of motion in Eq. (1) in $d = 1$ for $N = 5$ particles. The potential energy landscape U_i of each particle i is a sequence of parabolic wells with uniform curvature $\mu = 1$ and random widths (that are quenched). In this example, the landscape of each particle is drawn in a different colour. The particle positions u_i are indicated by the black dots. Their elastic interactions are schematically illustrated by black lines (with dashed lines indicating periodicity). The driving frame is indicated by a green line. It is connected to each particle by a weak spring of stiffness k_f illustrated using a dotted green line.

then follow the dynamics until the energy is minimized. This sequence is then repeated until we gathered sufficient statistics (discarding start-up effects). We save significantly on computational time using an event-driven algorithm, see Appendix B for details. These “events” are the primary object of most of our analysis. We drive using a weak⁵ spring of stiffness $k_f = 1/L^2$.

Triggering. The quasistatic response provides us with events at different forces f , whereby the response is purely elastic in between events. Since we are interested in the statistics of avalanches at fixed f , we additionally manually trigger avalanches at different f to efficiently gather sufficient statistics. Thereby, we move a randomly selected particle over the first barrier in the forward direction while keeping the position of the driving frame fixed, see Appendix C for details.

⁵The following scaling argument holds to set k_f . Because of the competition between disorder and elastic interactions, the interface gets a roughness $\delta u \sim \ell^\zeta$ (with ℓ a length). This corresponds to fluctuations of interactions $\delta f^n \sim k \partial^2 \delta u \sim k \ell^{\zeta-2}$ (with k the representative stiffness of the elastic interactions). The fluctuations of the drive are $\delta f^f \sim k_f \delta u \sim k_f \ell^\zeta$. For the disorder to be relevant $\delta f^n \sim \delta f^f$. Such that $k_f/k \sim 1/\ell^2$. The relevant length scale is the linear system size L , such that one should take $k_f/k \sim 1/L^2$ (whereby we have $k = 1$, see above).

3 Self-similarity

We consider the properties of the interface directly after system spanning events. The interface shape is a self-similar with a roughness exponent ζ . The fluctuations of position, δu , thus increase with length, ℓ , as

$$\delta u \sim \ell^\zeta. \quad (2)$$

We measure $\zeta \simeq 0.9$ in Fig. 4 using a simple “height-height correlation” of the position of the interface after system spanning events (in Appendix D we support this value using the structure factor). This value is intriguingly higher than the $\zeta = 0.63$ obtained for the same model using overdamped dynamics [45, 46]. Moreover, it is also significantly different from our earlier result of $\zeta = 0.60 \pm 0.08$ [42] based on long-range elasticity.

Figure 4. Correlation of the position of the interface u as a function of distance ℓ , after system spanning events, for different systems of size L (colours). The roughness exponent ζ is fitted on the power law range indicated using a full black line (the dotted black line is the fit’s extrapolation). See Fig. 5 and Appendix D for supporting measurements for the value of ζ .

4 Criticality

Disorder. Suppose that the global strength of the interface is f_c , but that spatial fluctuations exist. The strength of a region of extent ℓ is $f_c + \delta f_c(\ell)$. By definition, $\delta f_c(\ell \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow 0$. However, for finite ℓ there is a finite probability that the strength of a region is below (or above) f_c such that events of finite ℓ are possible if the interface is driven at $f = f_c$.

Avalanches. From the perspective of a propagating cascade of local failures (“avalanches”) this implies a finite probability that the avalanche can double in size. Consequently, criticality is ob-

served when the interface is driven at $f = f_c$, with avalanches whose properties are scale-free.

Fractal dimension. From the roughness, it follows that the accumulated total displacement S of an avalanche scales with its extent ℓ as

$$S \sim \int \delta u dx^d \sim \ell^{d+\zeta}, \quad (3)$$

where we integrate over d dimensions. Practically, we define the size S as the total number of fails, and the extent ℓ as the number of particles that fail at least once. Furthermore, we define f_c as the lowest force at which we find system spanning events (upon triggering at different forces). We verify Eq. (3) in Fig. 5 at $f \approx f_c$, which provides us with an uncertainty quantification $\zeta \simeq 0.9 \pm 0.1$. Note that we ignore system spanning events (which at f_c is only a small fraction of the events).

Figure 5. Measurement of the fractal dimension at $f \approx f_c$: the size S of avalanches as a function of their extent ℓ , with predicted scaling in Eq. (3) $S \sim \ell^{d+\zeta}$ as a dashed black line (see Table 1 for ζ). The solid black line shows a direct fit. The coloured markers correspond to a binning individual (manually triggered) avalanches for different L .

Size distribution. The avalanche’s size S and spatial extent ℓ (see Fig. 6) and are distributed

$$P(\ell) \sim \ell^{-\tau_\ell}, \quad P(S) \sim S^{-\tau}. \quad (4)$$

We measure $P(S)$ in Fig. 7 at $f \approx f_c$. We find an exponent $\tau \simeq 1.27$ that we support by a finite size collapse in the main panel. Furthermore, Eq. (3) can be used to express $\tau_\ell = 1 + d_f(\tau - 1)$, which we check in Appendix E. We note that the exponent τ

does not obey to the classical depinning prediction⁶.

Figure 6. Position of the interface u before (black) and after (green) an avalanche triggered at $f \approx f_c$. The total number of fails, S , is a proxy for the total displacement of the interface (in gray). The number of particles that fail at least once, ℓ (in $d = 1$), is a proxy for the linear extent of the avalanche (annotated).

Figure 7. Distribution of avalanche sizes, $P(S)$, at $f \approx f_c$. The scaling is indistinguishable from $P(S) \sim S^{-\tau}$ with $\tau = 1.27$. The inset shows the distributions for different L , the main panel shows the finite size collapse using exponents from Table 1.

5 Nucleation

A central result is that if $f - f_c \gg \delta f_c(\ell)$, the spatial fluctuations of strengths have become irrelevant, and the avalanche is unstable and cannot be

⁶For short range elasticity, depinning predicts $\tau = 2 - 2/(d + \zeta)$. With the measured roughness exponent $\zeta \simeq 0.9$ this predicts $\tau \simeq 0.95$ which clearly is not consistent with our data in Fig. 7. A similar discrepancy between overdamped and inertial dynamics was observed in amorphous solids [23, 24].

stopped. If $\delta f_c(\ell) \sim \ell^{-1/\nu}$, then avalanches are unstable if their extent

$$\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}. \quad (5)$$

The exponent ν is related to the roughness exponent ζ as follows. The roughness of the interface (Eq. (2)) corresponds to fluctuations of elastic interactions

$$\delta f \sim \ell^{\zeta-2}, \quad (6)$$

as follows from applying the Laplacian⁷ of term 2 in Eq. (1). Assuming that $\delta f \sim \delta f_c$, we find that

$$\nu = 1/(2 - \zeta). \quad (7)$$

We test this prediction using events triggered at different f . We consider the statistics biased on only those events that are avalanches (i.e. not system spanning, or $\ell < L$). We measure their maximum extent by estimating the cut-off ℓ_c , for which we use $\ell_c = \langle \ell^3 \rangle / \langle \ell^2 \rangle$. To properly test Eqs. (5) and (7) we employ a finite size collapse in Fig. 8 (cf. with its inset), and find our data to be reasonably consistent with our prediction. See Appendix F for supporting measurement based on a different protocol to extract ℓ_c .

Figure 8. Characterization of the nucleation length ℓ_c beyond which avalanches are unstable, as a function of force f . We define ℓ_c as the upper cut-off of the distribution of avalanche's linear extent: $\ell_c = \langle \ell^3 \rangle / \langle \ell^2 \rangle$ (with $\langle \dots \rangle$ the average over events that are not system spanning, i.e. $\ell < L$). The dotted line shows our prediction, with the roughness exponent ζ taken from Table 1.

6 Stick-slip in finite systems

Armouring. Despite the luring instability, the interface can be loaded at $f > f_c$ in a quasistat-

⁷In [42] the position of the interface corresponds to the slip u that was defined as a strain. The spatial fluctuations of the stress then correspond to the gradient of u , i.e. $\delta \sigma \sim \ell^{\zeta-1}$ if the roughness of the slip $\delta u \sim \ell^\zeta$.

Table 1. Scaling relations, predictions, and measured exponents in $d = 1$. Scaling relations marked “?” remain an open question.

Name	Expression	Scaling relation	Value	Measure
ζ	$\delta u \sim \ell^\zeta$	-	0.9	Fig. 4
d_f	$S \sim \ell^{d_f}$	$d_f = d + \zeta$	1.9	Fig. 5
τ	$P(S) \sim S^{-\tau}$?	1.27	Fig. 7
τ_ℓ	$P(\ell) \sim \ell^{-\tau_\ell}$	$\tau_\ell = 1 + d_f(\tau - 1)$	1.5	Fig. A2
ν	$\ell_c \sim f - f_c ^{-\nu}$	$\nu = 1/(2 - \zeta)$	0.9	Fig. 8
θ'	$n_a \sim (\Delta f)^{\theta'+1}$?	6.4	Fig. 9

ically driven system of finite size because of an “armouring” after a system spanning event. In particular, after a system spanning event the system stops at $f = f_{\min}$. Due to inertia, there are very few regions that yield if the force is increased by $\Delta f = f - f_{\min}$ [43]. If, at $f = f_{\min}$, the density of regions that can trigger a collective event vanishes as $P(x) \sim x^{\theta'}$, with x the amount of force needed to trigger a collective event, then increasing the load by Δf triggers a finite number of collective events

$$n_a \sim N \int_0^{\Delta f} P(x) dx \sim N (\Delta f)^{\theta'+1}, \quad (8)$$

with N the number of independent microscopic regions: the number of particles in our model. We measure $\theta' \simeq 6.4$ in Fig. 9 by comparing the cumulative number of a collective event upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event. Note that this exponent is non-trivially dependent on the activation barriers, see discussion in Appendix G.

Figure 9. Cumulative number of avalanches (whereby at least two particles fail), Φ , upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event. This allows fitting of the exponent θ' .

Bimodal distribution. The largest fraction of these collective events are what we call “avalanches”. These are events in which one or more, *but not all*, particles fail at least once, such that $\ell < L$. We quantify this observation in Fig. 10. In the main panel, the distribution of the event sizes $P(S)$ for different system sizes L shown using different colours. We clearly observe two populations of events: *avalanches* on the left and side, and *system spanning* events on the right-hand side⁸. The system spanning events are “slip” events during which the system accumulates macroscopic slip, while sub-extensive avalanches occur during the “stick” phase of the stick-slip cycle. The fraction of events that are avalanches is shown in the inset as a function of system size L . As observed, this fraction approaches one for large L .

Diverging length scale. The maximum size of the left part of the bimodal distribution in Fig. 10 is rationalized as follows. Because the number of avalanches is small, the underlying scale-free statistics are not observed in a quasistatically driven finite system. Instead, the typically largest observed avalanche extent follows from

$$n_a \int_{\ell_{\max}}^{\infty} P(\ell) d\ell \sim 1 \quad (9)$$

(as follows from extreme value statistics, see [47] for generic argument). If we assume that Eq. (4) holds at any Δf , then we practically observe a *diverging length scale*

$$\ell_{\max} \sim n_a^{-1/(1-\tau_\ell)} \sim N^{\frac{1}{\tau_\ell-1}} (\Delta f)^{\frac{\theta'+1}{\tau_\ell-1}} \quad (10)$$

when increasing the load by $\Delta f = f - f_{\min}$. In Fig. 11 we show the number of avalanches with a certain extent for avalanches triggered naturally during quasistatically loading in blue, and find that it is indeed qualitatively consistent with this prediction (shown in gold).

⁸These events hybridize in very small systems as included as illustration connecting e.g. to [28].

Figure 10. Distribution of the event sizes S of any event (“avalanche” or “system spanning”) during quasistatic loading, for different system sizes as indicated by the colour bar. *Avalanches*, cut-off at a small radius, constitute the majority of events (inset: fraction of events that are avalanches as a function of system size L). *System spanning*, or “slip”, events span the entire system, and constitute the right-hand side peak whose position increases with the system size L .

Nucleation of slip events. The nucleation of a system spanning slip events eventually happens when

$$\ell_{\max}(f_s) \sim \ell_c(f_s), \quad (11)$$

at a force f_s (that for frictional interfaces is proportional to the static friction coefficient). This corresponds to the intersection of the gold and red lines in Fig. 11.

Stick-slip amplitude. Let us, furthermore, assume that $f_{\min} \approx f_c$. Consequently, combining Eqs. (5) and (10) results in a prediction for the stick-slip amplitude

$$f_s - f_c \sim N^{-1/(\theta'+1-\nu(1-\tau_\ell))}. \quad (12)$$

To test this scaling prediction, we again consider the events acquired during normal quasistatic driving, and bias to system spanning events. In Fig. 12 we show in red the force f_s right before a system spanning event, and in blue the force f_{\min} right after it. An important observation is that the force after a system spanning event, f_{\min} , appears to converge to f_c , that we defined as the lowest force at which system spanning events are observed in our largest system. Indeed, we find $f_{\min}/f_c = 1.0013$ for the largest system, which corresponds to the error bar of f_{\min} . Crucially, the scaling of stick-slip amplitude $f_s - f_c$ is consistent with our prediction in Eq. (12), using the independently exponents and scaling relations summarized in Table 1, see inset

Figure 11. Spontaneous nucleation of slip during the stick-slip cycle in a finite system. Once stopped at f_{\min} after a slip event, the system is “armoured” such that there are very few regions close to yielding. In particular, if the density of regions that can trigger an avalanche vanishes as $P(x) \sim x^{\theta'}$, with x the amount of force needed to trigger an avalanche locally, the number of avalanches triggered upon increasing the load by $f - f_{\min}$ scales as $n \sim N(f - f_{\min})^{\theta'+1}$ with N the number of independent microscopic regions. With the linear extent ℓ distributed as $P(\ell) \sim \ell^{-\tau_\ell}$, the observed maximum avalanche size scales as $\ell_{\max} \sim N^{\frac{1}{\tau_\ell-1}}(f - f_{\min})^{\frac{\theta'+1}{\tau_\ell-1}}$. Once $\ell_{\max} \sim \ell_c \sim |f - f_c|^{-\nu}$, at f_s , the avalanche is unstable, starting the next slip event. In blue: the number of avalanches with a certain extent for avalanches triggered naturally during quasistatically, see colour bar. The lines corresponding to the predictions of ℓ_{\max} (gold) and ℓ_c (red) are based on measured exponents, but with arbitrary prefactors.

in Fig. 12. We emphasize that this is a costly measurement, that we have been able to perform only thanks to our very simple model.

7 Rheology

We have used two pragmatic definitions. f_c is the lowest force at which we find system spanning events. f_{\min} is the force at which the system stop after a system spanning event. In our numerics, the two are indistinguishable:

$$f_c \approx f_{\min}. \quad (13)$$

We now compare those forces to the flow curve of the interface, which we measure by driving the interface at a finite rate. A classical approach to stabilize the velocity-weakening instability, is to drive the system with a stiff spring [32]. We use $k_f = 0.1$ (as a reference, we note that we recorded the quasistatic response above for $k_f = 1/L^2 \approx 1.5 \times 10^{-8}$). We plot the flow curve in Fig. 13 and find that its minimum is indeed consistent with $f_{\min} \approx f_c$.

Figure 12. Main panel: Finite size scaling of the force just before system spanning events (f_s in red) and just after system spanning events (f_{\min} in blue). The markers correspond to the means and the error bars to the standard deviation. Inset: finite size scaling of the stick-slip amplitude $f_s - f_c$ with f_c the smallest force at which a system spanning event was found to occur in any of our finite systems (also shown in the main panel using a dashed black line). The dotted line corresponds to our prediction in Eq. (12), with exponents taken from Table 1.

Figure 13. Rheology of the inertial interface: the force f at the driving frame is a non-monotonic function of the velocity v . The measurement of the unstable branch (where $\partial_v f < 0$) is possible by driving with a stiff spring. Also indicated: the critical force f_c , defined the lowest force at which we find system spanning events.

8 Concluding remarks

We have presented a classical, simple, model of a driving elastic interface with disorder. Compared to well-established results in the context of the depinning transition, we considered inertial (instead of overdamped) dynamics. Like in our previous numerical observations based on a continuum model in dimension $d + 1$ [41, 42] we observe that:

- I The rheology of the interface is non-monotonic with a minimum in the force f vs slip rate v response at f_{\min} (Fig. 13).
- II When a quasistatically loaded system spanning events stop at f_{\min} . The geometry of the interface is self-similar with a roughness exponent ζ . At $f_c \approx f_{\min}$ the interface is critical, characterized by avalanches whose properties are distributed according to a power law, see Table 1.
- III At $f > f_c$ nucleation of an instability occurs when the avalanche extent $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$, with $\nu = 1/(2 - \zeta)$ (Fig. 8). Criticality (II) and nucleation (III) thereby protect an infinite system from loading beyond f_c . This results in a finite hysteresis of size $f_c - f_{\min}$, which we numerically measure to vanish in large systems.
- IV In a finite system, criticality is masked by stick-slip (Fig. 10). In particular: (IV-a) After system spanning events, the interface is armoured [43] such that avalanches are too rare to deny the interface to load beyond f_c (Fig. 9). (IV-b) Due to the rareness of events in practice, a growing length scale ℓ_{\max} of microscopic events is observed (Fig. 11). (IV-c) System spanning events eventually happen when $\ell_{\max} \sim \ell_c$.
- V By combining the previous facts, we obtain a prediction for the stick-slip amplitude $f_s - f_c$ as a function of the system size (Fig. 12).

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A Interactions

Following [45], we consider elastic interactions with a potential energy density that we expand to the

fourth order:

$$E(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}k_2(\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}))^2 + \frac{1}{12}k_4(\varepsilon(\mathbf{x}))^4, \quad (\text{A1})$$

with \mathbf{x} the spatial coordinate along the interface, k_2 and k_4 stiffnesses, and the gradient of the position $\varepsilon = \|\partial_{\mathbf{x}}u\|$. The resulting force $f^n(\mathbf{x}) = \text{div} \partial_{\varepsilon}E(\mathbf{x})$. In $d = 1$ the geometry corresponds to an elastic line, for which

$$f^n(x) = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \Big|_x \left(k_2 + k_4 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Big|_x \right)^2 \right), \quad (\text{A2})$$

which we discretize as [46]:

$$f_i^n = k_2[u_{i-1} - 2u_i + u_{i+1}] + k_4[(u_{i+1} - u_i)^3 + (u_i - u_{i-1})^3]. \quad (\text{A3})$$

We use $k_2 = k_4 = 1$ ⁹. Note that we have expressed x in units of the ‘discretization’ $h = 1$, such that the length of the line $L = N$. Finally, we assume periodic boundary conditions such that $u_0 = u_N$ ¹⁰.

B Event-driven quasistatic loading

Since the system is linear as long as no particle fails, we know the particle positions u_i satisfying the mechanical equilibrium for any driving frame position \bar{u} that matches the condition that all particles stay in their current potential well. This allows the following protocol. In alternation, we set $\bar{u}(t + \Delta t) = \bar{u}(t) + \Delta u(1 + \mu/k_f)$ and $u_i(t + \Delta t) = u_i(t) + \Delta u$ for all i , as follows. First, we perform a fully elastic step whereby the displacement Δu is chosen such that the particle closest to failing in the direction of driving ends at the verge of failing. In particular, $\Delta u = (\min(x_i)/\mu - \epsilon/2)_+$ (with the Macaulay brackets $(\dots)_+$ indicating that the term is zero if the argument is negative, and $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$). Since, by definition, no particle fails during this step, the system stays in mechanical equilibrium. Second, we apply a ‘kick’ and set $\Delta u = \epsilon$ followed by energy minimization using the dynamics in Eq. (1). Whatever happens during this step we refer to as an ‘event’, and they are the primary object of most of our analysis.

We collect the following number of events during quasistatic loading, for a system with L particles: $L = 2^5$: 357818, $L = 2^6$: 199964, $L = 2^7$: 199953, $L = 2^8$: 199934, $L = 2^9$: 84416, $L = 2^{10}$: 64224, $L = 2^{11}$: 72025, $L = 2^{12}$: 89594, $L = 2^{13}$: 32257.

⁹This model has as known limitation in $d = 1$ that linear elasticity ($k_4 = 0$) results in an unphysical roughness $\zeta > 1$, while $\zeta = 0.63$ if $k_4 > 0$ for overdamped dynamics [45, 46]. This is unimportant for our scaling prediction. However, we stick to the physical case of $\zeta < 1$ and choose $k_2 = k_4 = 1$ in $d = 1$.

¹⁰In fact, $u_{N+i} = u_i$ for any i .

C Triggering

For different f and starting from each system spanning event, we select the state with the highest $f_q < f$ acquired by normal quasistatic loading (hence the subscript q). We elastically load that state up to f (by advancing the driving frame by $\Delta\bar{u} = (f - f_q)/k_f$, and moving u_i accordingly to maintain mechanical equilibrium, see Appendix B). Then, while keeping the boundary condition \bar{u} fixed, we move a particle over the first barrier in the forward direction such that $u_i = u_i^{s+1} + \epsilon/2$ for a randomly selected¹¹ i and minimize energy. In practice, starting from each system spanning event, we load with different Δf and then bin on f .

D Roughness exponent ζ

The height-height correlation of the position of the interface (in Fig. 4) is verified using the structure factor of the interface, in Fig. A1. The structure factor $\hat{S}(q) \equiv \langle \hat{u}_p(q)\hat{u}_p(-q) \rangle$. Thereby, $u_p(r)$ is the unloaded position of the interface at location r (i.e. the position of the current local minimum of the potential energy landscape at location r). $\hat{u}_p(q)$ is the Fourier transform of $u_p(r)$, with q the wave vector. The average $\langle \dots \rangle$ is taken on independent snapshots after system spanning events. A self-affine interface with roughness exponent ζ is characterized by a scaling of the structure factor $\hat{S}(q) \sim q^{-(d+2\zeta)}$ as confirmed in Fig. A1 (see e.g. [48, 49] for discussions on the use of the structure factor to measure the roughness exponent of a self-affine interface).

E Extent distribution at f_c

Similar to Fig. 7 we measure the distribution of the avalanche extent, $P(\ell)$, at $f \approx f_c$. Its scaling is consistent with the measurement of τ in Fig. 7 together with the scaling relation for τ_ℓ in Table 1, see Fig. A2.

F Alternative measurement of ℓ_c

In the main text, we defined $\ell_c = \langle \ell^3 \rangle / \langle \ell^2 \rangle$. Here we use an alternative protocol where we fit an exponentially cut-off power law to the cumulative distribution $\Phi(\ell) \sim \ell^{1-\tau_\ell} \exp(-\ell/\ell_c)$, using the known exponent (see Table 1 and Figs. 4, 7 and A2). The

¹¹For a fraction of particles, the particle’s failure will not trigger an avalanche. To save on computational time, we rapidly assess, using entirely heuristic measures, if that is the case. If so, we select another particle. This does not result in any quantitative data about which particles are more likely to trigger an avalanche, since, without energy minimization, we cannot ensure if the particle truly did not trigger an avalanche. Precisely that energy minimization we chose to avoid by using heuristic rules, to save on computational time.

Figure A1. Structure factor of the interface after system spanning events for different systems of size L (colours). The scaling corresponding to a roughness with exponent ζ is shown using a straight black line (see text).

result in Fig. A3 is indeed also consistent with our prediction in Eqs. (5) and (7).

G Activation barriers

Activation barriers. The activation barriers after system spanning events contain information about the number of avalanches that can be triggered upon increasing the load. We measure x_i as the additional force needed to fail a particle i in the forward direction. The density $P(x)$ is consistent with a pseudo-gap distribution

$$P(x) \sim x^\theta, \quad (\text{A4})$$

see lower-left inset in Fig. A4. However, extracting θ from the noisy data is difficult. The proper measurement of the exponent is therefore to perform extreme value statistics using finite size scaling. Once again, we employ the result of [47] to argue that

$$N \int_0^{x_{\min}} P(x) dx \sim 1, \quad (\text{A5})$$

with $N \equiv L^d$ the number of particles. Assuming the pseudo-gap distribution of Eq. (A4), we find that $x_{\min} \sim N^{-1/(1+\theta)}$. Our data is consistent with this result with $\theta = 3.2$ as shown in the main panel of Fig. A4. This result is not far from our earlier result of $\theta = 3.7$ [41] in our model based on long-range elasticity. Furthermore, this value is of the same order as a prediction based on a single particle model [43].

Overcoming barriers. We define θ' based on the actual number of avalanches (in which at least two particles fail) upon increasing the load by Δf after

Figure A2. Distribution of avalanche extent, $P(\ell)$, at $f \approx f_c$. The scaling from the measurement of τ in Fig. 7 together with the scaling relation for τ_ℓ in Table 1 is shown using a black line. The inset shows $P(\ell)$ and the main panel the finite size collapse with that value of τ_ℓ .

a system spanning event. Intriguingly, we find that $\theta' \simeq 6.4 > \theta$, cf Figs. 9 and A4. Like in [41] we thus find that not all failures trigger an avalanche. However, here, we find even more failures that do not trigger an avalanche. This underlines that the armouring, in which small barriers are rare, is further strengthened by the fact the interface is stable to overcoming some of the small barriers – metastability is only experienced in a fraction of failures. It, however, needs further investigation.

H Stability of rate-and-state friction

Consider a single particle with mass m that is driven by a spring of stiffness k_f . Furthermore, it is subjected to velocity weakening rate-and-state friction. In such a model, the friction force

$$f_p = f_0 + a \ln(v_i/v_0) + b \ln(v_0\tau/D_c). \quad (\text{A6})$$

Here, f_0 , a , and b are parameters with the units of force here; v_0 sets the units of velocity; τ is the age of the interface; and D_c is the sliding distance needed to rejuvenate the interface. We complement this law with a simple ageing law

$$\dot{\tau} = 1 - v_i\tau/D_c. \quad (\text{A7})$$

For this law, the steady state age, after rejuvenation has completed, corresponds to

$$\tau_\infty = D_c/v_i. \quad (\text{A8})$$

We stabilize this rheology by adding a viscous term ηv_i .

In the steady state, the resulting rheology is non-monotonic with a minimum at $v_c = (b - a)/\eta$. The

Figure A3. Complementary to Fig. 8 we measure ℓ_c by fitting an exponential cut-off to the cumulative distribution of the linear extent of avalanches (see text), and verify that our data is consistent with the prediction in Eqs. (5) and (7).

Figure A4. Characterization of (force) barriers after system spanning events. The force needed to trigger failure locally $x_i \equiv \mu(u_i^Y - u_i)$. Plotted is x_{\min} as a function of the number of particles N , which allows fitting the exponent θ of $P(x) \sim x^\theta$ as indicated (see also main text). x_{\min} is taken as the mean of the minimum of x after n system spanning events, see Appendix B. Lower-left inset: $P(x)$ for different system sizes. Upper-right inset: cumulative number of events upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event. In both cases, the black line corresponds the θ fitted in the main plot.

unstable branch, where $\partial_v f < 0$ corresponds to $v < v_c$. The stable branch, where $\partial_v f > 0$ corresponds to $v > v_c$.

Supposing that the particle is in a steady state in mechanical equilibrium (such that the particle exactly follows the drive as $v_i = v$), force balance corresponds to

$$\underbrace{f_0 + a \ln\left(\frac{v}{v_0}\right) + b \ln\left(\frac{v_0 \tau_\infty}{D_c}\right)}_{\text{rate-and-state}} + \underbrace{\eta v}_{\text{heat}} = \underbrace{k_f(vt - u_i)}_{\text{drive}}. \quad (\text{A9})$$

We will now consider the effect of a small perturbation $v + \delta v$, $\tau_\infty + \delta\tau$, and $u_i + \delta u$. This results in

$$\delta v(a/v + \eta) + \delta\tau b/\tau_\infty = -k_f \delta u. \quad (\text{A10})$$

Applying the same perturbation to the ageing law (still around the steady state) results in

$$\delta \dot{\tau} = -\delta v/v - \delta\tau/\tau_\infty. \quad (\text{A11})$$

Combining it with the time derivative of Eq. (A10) results in

$$\begin{cases} \delta \dot{v}(a/v + \eta) + \delta \dot{\tau} b/\tau_\infty = -k_f \delta v \\ \delta \dot{\tau} = -\delta v/v - \delta\tau/\tau_\infty \end{cases} \quad (\text{A12})$$

Let us make the ansatz $\delta v = v_0 e^{\lambda t}$ and $\delta\tau = \tau_0 e^{\lambda t}$ (with λ a complex number) and search for solutions. After some algebra, we find

$$\lambda^2 \left(\frac{a}{v} + \eta\right) + \lambda \left(\frac{a - b + \eta v}{D_c} + k_f\right) + \frac{k_f v}{D_c} = 0 \quad (\text{A13})$$

Now, the perturbation will grow exponentially in time if $\text{Re}(\lambda) > 0$, while they will decay exponentially if $\text{Re}(\lambda) < 0$. The critical case therefore corresponds to $\text{Re}(\lambda_c) = 0$, such that $\lambda_c = i\text{Im}(\lambda)$. This implies that $-\text{Im}(\lambda_c)(a/v + \eta) + k_f v/D_c = 0$ and $\text{Im}(\lambda_c)((a - b + \eta v)/D_c + k_f) = 0$. From the latter, it follows that the critical stiffness is

$$k_f = (b - a - \eta v)/D_c \equiv k_c. \quad (\text{A14})$$

If $k_f < k_c$, a perturbation will grow exponentially, and the system is unstable. If $k_f > k_c$, a perturbation will decay exponentially, and the system is stable. In this case, the particle will not show stick-slip even if driven at a rate $v < v_c$.

I Measuring f_{\min}

Driven interface. We measure the rheology of our model by driving the system at a finite rate v ¹² and measuring the average force experienced by

¹²At every time step we move the driving frame $\bar{u}(t + \Delta t) = \bar{u}(t) + v\Delta t$.

Figure A5. Simple model of a single particle subject to a rate-and-state friction force and heat radiation, and driving at a velocity v by a weak spring of stiffness k_f .

the driving frame f . We consider only the steady state response. Any transient start-up effects or intermittent response is discarded. We consider our largest system $L = 2^{13}$ and measure the rheology for different stiffnesses k_f (as a reference, we note that we recorded the quasistatic response above for $k_f = 1/L^2 \approx 1.5 \times 10^{-8}$). The results are shown in Fig. A6. The different blue curves correspond to different stiffnesses k_f (see colour bar). The non-monotonic rheology is evidenced when driving with a stiff spring. However, the rheology is an interplay between the response of the interface and the driving spring as clearly observed. We do not understand the details of this interplay, and from Fig. A6 it seems non-trivial, as the order of the curves is not monotonic in k_f . Objectively extracting f_{\min} (and v_{\min}) from this data is therefore currently not possible, and future work is urged.

Relaxation. We propose an alternative protocol to measure the rheology. We measure the relaxation during a system spanning slip event during quasistatic loading. In particular, we measure the force experienced by the driving frame, f , as a function of the average velocity of the interface, v . The result is shown in Fig. A6 using a green curve. This protocol cannot acquire the unstable branch of the rheology, but it does allow measuring the stable branch. It is tempting to speculate that it does so until $v = v_c$. If that is the case, we find a good agreement between the minimum of the rheology, f_{\min} , and the definition of f_c that we used above.

J Radiation damping

In a d dimensional interface embedded in a $d+1$ dimensional elastic medium, also the inertia of the medium has a stabilization effect known as “radiation damping” [40]. Let us consider a system with very weak background damping, for example because only little energy is lost at the system’s boundaries. Suppose that the resistance of the pinning potential as a function of velocity is $f^p(v)$. Then, during flow, the remote force f measured at the system’s boundaries is $f = f^p(v) + \eta v$, with η the background damping, see Fig. A7b. A nucleating event, whereby part of the interface and bulk

Figure A6. For the largest system. Green curve: relaxation measurement: during a system spanning event the force and velocity are measured. The shown data is the average force per bin of velocity. The large square green markers correspond to measurements of the force if the system is driven at a constant finite rate. Measurements in which the system intermittently stops are discarded. The same type of measurement is shown for different driving stiffnesses in blue (see colour bar).

are still static as the rupture invades the interface, is stabilized by the bulk surrounding it: to increase the velocity v , the bulk around the rupture has to be accelerated. The costs of this acceleration lead to a remote force $f = f^p(v) + (\mu/(2c_v))v$, with μ the shear modulus of the bulk, and $c_s = \sqrt{\mu/\rho}$ the shear wave speed of the bulk, with ρ the mass density of the bulk, see Fig. A7a. Because the bulk is accelerated by elastic waves that radiate away from the interface this effect is commonly referred to as “radiation damping”.

In the case that $\eta \ll \mu/(2c_v)$ the stick-slip cycle of a thermodynamic system is now as follows. During nucleation, the net velocity of the interface is zero, and the flow curve is stabilized by radiation damping with a minimum at f_{\min}^{nucl} , see Fig. A7a. As above, slip starts if $f = f_c > f_{\min}^{\text{nucl}}$. Once moving, the radiation damping term disappears and the flow curve is lowered with a minimum at f_{\min}^{flow} , see Fig. A7b. The system thus stops if $f = f_{\min}^{\text{flow}} < f_{\min}^{\text{nucl}} < f_c$. This corresponds to the stick-slip cycle shown in Figs. A7c and A7d.

We expect criticality to be observed at $f = f_c$. As before, we expect an instability if an avalanche’s extent $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$. However, by the same argument, we expect avalanches at $f < f_c$ to be sub-extensive such that the distribution of their extent $P(\ell)$ is cut off at $\ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$ for which we expect the same exponent to hold. We qualitatively confirmed this picture using the model of [41, 42], but lack a quantitative confirmation, which is left

for future work.

Figure A7. [Sketch] In a d dimensional interface embedded in a $d + 1$ dimensional elastic medium, also the inertia of the medium has a stabilization effect known as “radiation damping”. Flow low background damping, this can lead to an additional source of hysteresis. (a) During nucleation, the background damping is dominated by radiation damping leading to a non-monotonic flow curve with a minimum at f_{\min}^{nucl} . (b) Once moving, the radiation damping term disappears and the flow curve is lowered with a minimum at f_{\min}^{flow} . (c,d) Quasistatic loading of the interface in the thermodynamic limit results in stick-slip whereby slip nucleates at $f_c > f_{\min}^{\text{nucl}}$ and stops at $f_{\min}^{\text{flow}} < f_{\min}^{\text{nucl}} < f_c$, as indicated with arrows and corresponding colours.

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